

Training materials on organic cultivar testing, OV and OHM

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LiveSeeding - Organic seed and plant breeding to accelerate sustainable and diverse food systems in Europe is a 4-year Innovation Action funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). The project started in October 2022 and brings together 37 organisations operating in 16 European countries. LiveSeeding provides science-based evidence and best practice solutions to help achieve 100 % organic seed.

LiveSeeding contributes to the transition towards environmentally-friendly, climate-neutral, healthy and fair food systems through a **PUSH-PULL-ENABLE strategy** to

- enhance the availability and adequacy of organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PUSH),
- increase and stabilise the market demand for organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PULL),
- foster an enabling policy and regulatory environment where both demand and supply can harmoniously and productively negotiate without irrelevant constraints due to legal restrictions and/or regulatory fragmentation (ENABLE).

LiveSeeding addresses the topics in a **holistic multi-actor, multi-stakeholder, participatory approach** involving stakeholders along the value chain in 17 local **Living Labs** (LLs) and 3 established networks of organic breeders (**ECO-PB**), seed savers (**ECLLD**) and Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (**MUFPP**). 15 European countries cover the different pedoclimatic zones and socio-economic contexts, including countries with a low level of development in organic seed and breeding in East and South Europe.

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List of abbreviations

BSc	Bachelor of Science
CET	Cultivar Evaluation Trials
CPVO	Community Plant Variety Office
DUS	Distinctness, Uniformity, Stability
ECO-PB	European Consortium for Organic Plant Breeding
EU	European Union
MSc	Master of Science
OHM	Organic Heterogeneous Material
OV	Organic Varieties
PhD	Doctor of Philosophy
PRM	Plant Reproductive Material
VCU	Value for Cultivation and Use
WP	Work Package

Summary

The present deliverable compiles training materials on cultivar¹ evaluation methods, on the registration processes for organic varieties (OV) and on the notification process for organic heterogeneous materials (OHM).

Its foundation is the EU Organic Regulation 848/2018, which stresses that - given the limited use of external inputs (fertilizers, pesticides) - cultivar selection is a crucial issue in organic farming. This calls for evaluation models and practices that assess cultivar performance under real-life farming conditions and meet the diversity needs of organic systems.

The document is structured into five modules covering the full process from basic concepts to digital tool use, namely:

- **Module 6** – Definition and registration of organic varieties: breeding requirements, preparation of DUS (distinctness, uniformity, stability) test proposals, VCU, and intellectual property considerations.
- **Module 7** – Notification of organic heterogeneous materials (OHM): specific rules, official quality control, and examples from current EU practices.
- **Module 8** – Methodology of participatory variety trials: “frugal” (simplified) trial design, farmer involvement, and European case studies.
- **Module 9** – Data management for on-farm cultivar evaluation trials: ensuring FAIR data, statistical readiness, and hands-on examples.
- **Module 10** – Digital tools (e.g. SeedLinked, ClimMob, AgriPartner) supporting data collection, evaluation, and farmer knowledge exchange, with a focus on SeedLinked.

Each module defines its learning objectives, target audience, training methods, and assessment approaches. Materials are provided in multiple formats, including lecture slides, recorded videos, webinars, case studies, practical exercises and online quizzes.

The ultimate aim is to promote the use of **100% organic seeds and varieties in Europe**, strengthen the capacity of farmers, breeders, and regulatory authorities, and foster the development of innovative and sustainable agroecosystems.

¹ The term (organic) cultivar is used as the generic term of reference for (organic) varieties, breeding lines, landraces, populations and Organic Heterogenous Material (Organic Regulation 2018/848/EU).

Justification and main objectives

“The Organic Regulation EU 848/2018 recognises the priority of developing and testing cultivars suitable to organic agriculture. When the use of external inputs such as mineral fertilizers, herbicides, and pesticides -tools that help mitigate environmental stress and buffer variation- is restricted or excluded, the choice of cultivar becomes the most important crop-specific decision available to organic farmers.

Under organic conditions, cultivar adaptation to farming systems, the environment and the market in which farmers operate can only be ensured by an optimal information flow about cultivars’ performance. Such flow of information can be enabled, in turn, by appropriate cultivar evaluation. In conventional agriculture, post-registration cultivar evaluation is mainly performed on controlled experimental sites and its results are used by extension services to provide variety recommendations for farmers. This system requires a great investment in terms of logistics and infrastructure and is extremely labour and cost intensive, while providing information of limited relevance to organic farmers.

As organic agriculture continues to make up a distinct but still smaller segment of the overall agricultural sector, there are relatively few cultivar evaluation programmes in Europe specifically designed for organic systems. Most of these adopt the same framework as conventional programmes and are focused on a limited number of major crops. Therefore, they are far from responding to the complex information needs required by the highly diverse organic systems.

To overcome this lock-in, radical innovation pathways are needed, to explore innovative models for cultivar evaluation under Organic Agriculture.” (Rey et al., 2021, pp. 5–6).” It also focuses on the registration of organic varieties, presenting the requirements for breeding, the definition of organic varieties, the preparation of DUS test proposals, and VCU and intellectual property considerations. It also describes the procedure for notifying organic heterogeneous material (OHM), with particular regard to special rules, official quality controls, and EU practices that are still partially implemented (Rey et al., 2021, ch. 1.2–1.3).

LiveSeeding project aims to enhance the availability and adequacy of organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming. **Training modules on organic cultivar testing, organic varieties (OV), and organic heterogeneous material (OHM), key concepts, terms, strategies,** and tools available **represent a key enabler to change farming practices.**

Deliverable D2.4 is a compilation of **training materials in cultivar testing, organic varieties and organic heterogeneous materials**, conceived for a public of

stakeholders that would be dealing with (i) the constitution and registration/notification of Organic Varieties of OHM and, more in general, with (ii) cultivar evaluation as part of their activity. The target audience is supposed to be larger than the professionals of breeding and cultivar evaluation, so as to include various sorts of multi-actor communities, such as farmers groups or value chains, who would be undertake the challenge of collectively managing genetic resources and seeds whilst experimenting and diversifying organisational and business models.

Description of the training modules and methodology

Training materials are divided into five thematic modules, structured in 3-5 units each, covering from the basic aspects of cultivar testing, OV and OHM to the most sophisticated available tools, all respectful of the principles of organic production.

Each training module has a training outline that clearly identifies the scope of the training, the learning objectives and target audience, the learning modalities, methodology and materials, as well as the learning assessment method. The training outline has been developed as a common approach for all training materials and training-related quizzes in the project. The supporting materials include i) PowerPoint presentations prepared by the lecturers; ii) the video recordings of the units; iii) other support learning materials such as webinar recordings, infographics, exercises, case studies etc. & iv) the training outline for each Module.

The training courses are organized into five thematic modules, each divided into three to five units. Most units can be delivered as online "self-directed" learning modules, combining webinars, presentations, and quizzes.

The modules are numbered 6 to 10 as they are a continuum from the first five training modules on organic breeding (WP1).

The modules and their corresponding links in Organic Eprints and ECO-PB are:

Module 6: *What is an organic variety and how to register it? (4 units).*

Organic Eprint link: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56300/>

ECO PB: <https://www.eco-pb.org/publications/liveseeding.html>

Module 7: *What is organic heterogeneous material and how to notify it? (5 units).*

Organic Eprint link: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56302/>

ECO PB: <https://www.eco-pb.org/publications/liveseeding.html>

Module 8: *Participatory trial methodology: how to design and monitor participatory cultivar evaluation trials (4 units)*

Organic Eprint link: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56304/>

ECO PB: <https://www.eco-pb.org/publications/liveseeding.html>

Module 9: *Data management in on-farm cultivar evaluation trials (4 units).* [SharePoint link](#)

Organic Eprint link: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56306/>

ECO PB: <https://www.eco-pb.org/publications/liveseeding.html>

Module 10: *Organic heterogeneous material (OHM) design and development (5 units).*

Organic Eprint link: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56307/>

ECO PB: <https://www.eco-pb.org/publications/liveseeding.html>

All training modules follow a **common training outline** that clearly defines the scope, learning objectives, target audience, learning modalities, methodology and materials, as well as the assessment method. This outline, together with the **modular approach**, was developed -as a shared framework for all training materials and training-related deliverables in the project (each work package including a training task)- by **Stéphanie Mothes (ITAB, FR)** with the support of **Mariano Iossa (FiBL Europe)** and **Francesca Gori (RSR)** within the work of the Training Task Force (T7.2).

The aim is to build coherent learning paths that facilitate knowledge transfer and ensure the easy replicability of trainings. The modular approach also makes it possible to design new trainings in the future by combining individual modules or units from different work packages, thereby creating targeted programmes for specific audiences and learning needs.

To develop the content of each module, several workshops were organised within Work Package 2 of LiveSeeding, led by the related Task 2.5 Leader (Gyöngyi Györéné Kis - ÖMKi) and involving both the Task Leaders (Abco de Buck - LBI, Carl Vollenweider and Maïke Bender – DFH, Ambrogio Ciostanzo - ITAB, Amritbir Riar – FiBL), and WP2 Leaders (Frédéric Rey – ITAB, Charlotte Bickler/Julia Cooper – ORC).

Module 6 - What is an organic variety and how to register it?

Materials available on: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56300/>

Links to the quizzes or other exercises:

Unit 6.1: <https://forms.gle/YVdbHSZ7E6XgTySF8>

Unit 6.2: <https://forms.gle/cxdovirv3eqtpZT7A>

Number of units: 4

Topics: This training module serves as a practical guideline for breeders. It covers:

1. the requirements for organic breeding and the definition of an organic variety;
2. how to register an organic variety, including the use or development of an adapted DUS protocol for a given crop species;
3. key aspects of VCU (Value for Cultivation and Use) and IPR (Intellectual Property Rights).

Target groups: breeders of vegetable and arable crops that are actively involved in the registration process with the national authorities.

Learning objectives: At the end of the training, the trainee received input and contacts to support:

- Be able to understand or carry out the full procedure for registering an organic variety for a specific crop species.

Unit 6.1 - Definition of organic breeding and organic variety

Lecturer(s): Abco de Buck, PhD

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Louis Bolk Institute (LBI)

Unit duration: 30 min

Topics: The EU Organic Regulation (2018/848), in force since 2022, promotes the development of organic varieties (OVs) suitable for organic production. OVs originate from organic plant breeding programmes in which all breeding steps are carried out under organic conditions, respecting genetic diversity and the natural reproductive capacity of plants. The definition also emphasises the exclusion of GMOs, cell fusion, and other technical interventions, while ensuring transparency and traceability throughout the process.

To enable OVs to access the market, they must be registered and pass official registration tests. The LiveSeeding project has proposed adapted protocols for these tests — DUS (Distinctness, Uniformity, Stability) and VCU (Value for Cultivation and

Use) — to be conducted under organic conditions. The aim is to establish clear regulations tailored to the specific needs of the organic sector.

Unit 6.2 - How to register an organic variety / VCU / IPR aspects

Lecturer(s): Abco de Buck, PhD

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Louis Bolk Institute (LBI)

Topics: To enable the acceptance of OV, DUS and VCU tests must be adapted to organic conditions. Two video presentations from the OV webinars emphasise the need for more flexible protocols that account for greater genetic diversity, while still meeting market and agronomic requirements. VCU tests should be conducted at multiple locations under organic farming conditions to provide a realistic assessment of variety performance. The goal is to make organic DUS and VCU protocols available for as many plant species as possible by 2029 — when the current derogation expires — with the support of the CPVO and national examination offices, thereby securing market access for organic breeders.

This unit provides two video presentations with existing proposals (e.g. carrot, wheat) and examples of organic VCU, self-declaration for an OV, and a spreadsheet version on ECO-PB site.

Unit duration: 30 min

Unit 6.3 and 6.4 - Giving examples and practical tips

Lecturer(s): Abco de Buck, PhD

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Louis Bolk Institute (LBI)

Topics: This unit provides a collection of links on the registration of OVs in the ECO-PB website and the Zucchini case study. It also illustrates the key differences of different plant breeding methods, via an infographic entitled Registration of Organic Varieties with a higher degree of diversity.

Unit duration: 20 min

Module 7 - What is organic heterogeneous material and how to notify it?

Materials available on: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56302/>

Links to the quizzes or other exercises:

Unit 7.1: <https://forms.gle/FhCSQUYvxvixEmAq6>

Unit 7.2: <https://forms.gle/M4WG1i7MvmGqDQ468>

Unit 7.3: <https://forms.gle/JPAYjDgsWH1BhNM2A>

Unit 7.4: <https://forms.gle/8vevQxfVofevwnEY8>

Unit 7.5: <https://forms.gle/W8byTQg2ndgm1isx6>

Topics: In this module, participants gain an introduction to organic heterogeneous material (OHM) and its notification procedure. Notification and official quality control procedures for OHM follow specific rules that differ significantly from those for standard varieties. Currently, these procedures for plant reproductive material (PRM) of OHM are only partially implemented in some EU Member States, meaning that information and advisory services remain limited.

This module provides basic knowledge on the notification of vegetable and cereal OHM. By the end of the course, trainees will be able to complete the notification template, submit an OHM notification, and develop and implement their own template and procedure.

Training materials include a webinar, videos, and PowerPoint presentations, complemented by a booklet and relevant literature on the topic.

Number of units: 5

Target groups: This module is open to seed networks managers and facilitators, a wide range of breeders, producers of PRM of OHM and other stakeholders therefore require additional information and consulting services about these procedures.

Learning objectives: At the end of the training, the trainee will be able to:

- Seed companies / farmers (notifier): Fill in the notification template and notify OHM (if a notification procedure already exists)
- National authorities' agents: develop a notification template and implement a notification procedure suitable for their countries (in case there is no notification process until now)

Unit 7.1 - Introducing the topic – OHM at Dottenfelderhof

Lecturer(s): Carl Vollenweider, PhD

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Dottenfelder Bio-Saat

Unit duration: 14 min

Topics: As an organic plant breeder and researcher, Carl Vollenweider provides insights into practical work with organic heterogeneous material (OHM). The video shows interesting data on the cultivation area of OHM from Dottenfelderhof in Germany, as well as results from field trials with OHM, which demonstrate the great potential of winter wheat OHM compared to certified varieties. The seed production of OHM and seed multiplication are also topics covered in the video. Finally, a first look is taken at the situation of OHM in Europe.

Unit 7.2 - How to set up a notification procedure?

External partner(s): Seeds4All and Artemisia AIBSL

Unit duration: 12 min

Topics: Since 2022, the European Regulation on organic production allows all operators to market seeds of organic heterogeneous material (OHM) — a new category of seed that can be used in organic farming, home gardening, and even conventional farming.

This video explains the new regime step-by-step and shows how easy it is to enter the market, supporting the growth of the organic sector, expanding its consumer base, and helping to restore agrobiodiversity.

The video is structured into 10 chapters: 1. Definition, 2. Marketing conditions, 3. Description & notification, 4. Breeding or production techniques, 5. Quality standards, 6. Labelling & packaging, 7. Traceability, 8. Controls, 9. Maintenance, 10. Database listing.

Unit 7.3 - How to notify an OHM?

Lecturer(s): Maike Bender

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Dottenfelder Bio-Saat

Unit duration: 7 min

Topics: As a new cultivar category, the notification of organic heterogeneous material (OHM) is relatively recent and may appear complex to operators. From preparing the notification dossier to the review phase and the marketing of plant reproductive material, the video outlines the key steps in the OHM notification process. Alongside explanations, it provides important practical guidance for each stage.

Unit 7.4 - Giving examples – OHM in Europe

Lecturer(s): Maike Bender

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Dottenfelder Bio-Saat

Unit duration: 8 min

Topics: This video provides an overview of organic heterogeneous material (OHM) that has already been notified in Europe. Since OHM has a great potential to increase the resilience and genetic diversity of organic farming systems, it is encouraging to see its current widespread use. Its importance continues to grow, particularly within the organic farming sector. This data collection highlights the promising future of OHM and underlines the need to continue monitoring its development.

Unit 7.5 - Practical tips/ exercise on how to do it

Lecturer(s): Aishwarya Chettia

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Dottenfelder Bio-Saat

Unit duration: 9 min

Topics: Since the notification dossier is the most critical part of the procedure for notifying organic heterogeneous material (OHM), this video offers practical tips on how to prepare it and key points to keep in mind. The OHM description in the notification forms the foundation of a functional marketing system for OHM. Therefore, the video explains the main elements of the description as set out in the Organic Regulation (EU) 2018/848 and the Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/1189. Among other aspects, it focuses on phenotypic characterisation, relevant traits, and the breeding technique.

Module 8 - Participatory trial methodology: how to design and monitor participatory cultivar evaluation trials

Materials available on: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56304/>

Links to the quizzes or other exercises:

Unit 8.1 & 8.2: Quiz

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeJOfn3KYXVx1FbdTw1RVnUIP6CC0viFS_w3NM0mBPYdUWOUA/viewform

Unit 8.3: Citizen science exercise and Unit 8.4: Scenario exercise:

<https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56304/>

Topics: This module covers organic cultivar trial models, focusing on the transition from traditional, centralised and technician-managed plot trials to participatory and decentralised methodologies, emphasizing a more collaborative and farmer-centered approach to agricultural research. Participants will gain an understanding of participatory methodologies and the practical tools used to engage stakeholders, especially farmers, in the co-creation and assessment of on-farm experiments. Whilst post-registration cultivar evaluation is the main topic, this module can be mobilised whenever the evaluation and documentation of differences between genetic resources is necessary to support decisions and, more in general, can inspire an alternative design of any experimentation relevant to organic farming and agroecology.

The course provides an overview of key participatory methods, including facilitation techniques, data collection strategies, and decision-making frameworks that promote shared learning and ownership of the process and the results. Through real-world case studies from the UK, Italy, France, Portugal, and Spain, participants will explore how these methodologies have been successfully applied in diverse agricultural and cultural contexts.

A hands-on trial design simulation will allow participants to apply their knowledge by collaboratively designing a participatory trial, reinforcing the principles and challenges of this approach. By the end of the training, attendees will be equipped with the knowledge and practical skills to implement participatory observation in their own agricultural research and extension activities.

Number of units: 4

Target groups: In this module, the targeted trainees will learn about the most relevant particularities, methodologies and strategies related and aimed at organic cultivar evaluation.

This module is open to breeders, agronomists, technicians, seed networks managers and facilitators, a wide range of organic farmers (particular interest for farmers committed with agroecology, preservation of landraces and starting in breeding their own varieties), students (mainly university BSc, MSc or even PhD), with an interest in plant breeding for organic and low-input farming.

Learning objectives: At the end of the training, the trainee should be able to:

- To be able to compare and contrast conventional cultivar evaluation with on-farm, decentralized evaluation, and justify the benefits of decentralized evaluation for organic farming systems.
- To be able to describe the principle of frugality in on-farm cultivar evaluation and analyse its practical applications for resource-efficient trials.
- To be able to explain the 'objectives-constraints-methods' approach to trial design and apply it to develop a practical on-farm evaluation plan.
- To be able to use a decision tree to identify the most appropriate trial design based on specific criteria for on-farm cultivar evaluation.
- To be able to critically evaluate on-farm cultivar evaluation case studies against the 10 principles of frugal innovation.

Unit 8.1 – Moving from traditional plot trials to “frugal” trial design

Lecturer(s): Julia Cooper, PhD

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Organic Research Centre (ORC)

Unit duration: 1h30

Topics: This section of the training focuses on the shift from traditional, researcher-led plot trials to participatory observation approaches in agricultural research. While plot trials are typically conducted under controlled conditions with limited farmer involvement, participatory observation emphasizes collaboration with farmers in real-world settings. This method values local knowledge, encourages shared decision-making, and fosters mutual learning. In this unit the key terminology is introduced; content is reinforced through listening to a webinar on on-farm cultivar evaluation trials (CET) and discussing the webinar with peers. The objectives-constraints-methods approach is covered.

Unit 8.2 - Designs for on-farm cultivar evaluation & LIVESEED case studies

Lecturer(s): Julia Cooper, PhD

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Organic Research Centre (ORC)

Unit duration: 1h20

Topics: This unit uses the decision trees developed in the LIVESEED project to guide the learner to an appropriate design for an on-farm cultivar evaluation trial. Key factors to consider include: numbers of varieties, numbers of farms involved, goals of the evaluation, resources and expertise available. Case studies from the LIVESEED project's activities in Hungary and Slovakia are reviewed and critiqued to broaden the learner's understanding of the many forms that participatory cultivar evaluation can take. A quiz is provided on content in Unit 1 & 2.

Unit 8.3 – In-depth case study on tricot design and frugal innovation

Lecturer(s): Julia Cooper, PhD

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Organic Research Centre (ORC)

Unit duration: 1h10

Topics: In this section the learners listen to a webinar on a specific example of participatory cultivar evaluation using the tricot approach. They are provided with guiding questions to help them explore how this example aligns with the principles of frugal innovation. When offered in real-time, the unit requires learners to work in pairs and prepare a short presentation on their findings. This will help them to consolidate learning on frugal innovation and build skills in communication on cultivar evaluation trials design.

Unit 8.4 - Trial design simulation (optional activity outside of scheduled teaching time)

Lecturer(s): Julia Cooper, PhD

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Organic Research Centre (ORC)

Unit duration: 3h

Topics: In this self-directed learning activity participants are introduced to four different hypothetical scenarios where cultivar evaluation trials are proposed. For each scenario they produce a paragraph indicating which design type (from the design trees presented in Units 1 & 2) they believe is most appropriate. This activity will further consolidate the learner's skills in using the decision trees and help them to build skills in critically evaluating situations and applying what they have learned.

Module 9 - Data management and analysis: how to analyse data from on-farm cultivar evaluation trials

Materials available on: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56306/>

Links to the quizzes or other exercises:

Unit 9.1 & 9.2: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdSssDfhr6tbr5eXqzc_w-CdrkHtoNmeu2ELbROEKHZnYMw/formResponse

Unit 9.3 & 9.4: Trainees participate in a variety of self-directed learning activities in Unit 9.3 and create their own Data Management Plan in Unit 9.4. These activities can be assessed by peers or the instructor. <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56306/>

Topics: This module shows trainees how to manage data generated from on-farm cultivar evaluation trials so that it is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) and formatted ready for statistical analysis. Participants will learn how to write a data management plan which acts as the foundation for robust management of data ensuring the highest quality and integrity of their data, supporting transparency and reproducibility. Practical exercises using tools for data collection, as well as critiquing and drafting a DMP ensure that the learner has the skills needed to effectively manage data from on-farm CETs.

Number of units: 4

Target groups: On-farm participatory trials are typically designed by researchers who may be working for farmer cooperatives or networks interested in developing and/or screening genetically diverse crop materials for performance in their local environment. Researchers may also be employed by small, local seed companies interested in identifying seeds suitable for their local market. Therefore, this training is targeted towards researchers or trial managers. There is an expectation that the typical trainee is computer literate with proficiency in MS Excel or an equivalent software for data entry and manipulation. Ideally, they should have some background in basic statistics, understanding the principles of trial design such as managing for environmental variables and the importance of control treatments.

Learning objectives: At the end of the training, the trainee should be able:

- To demonstrate skills in data organisation including appropriate data documentation.
- To understand and operationalise FAIR data principles.
- To be familiar with GDPR and implement data management practices that comply with this regulation.
- To demonstrate how to build datasets that are accessible and interoperable using clearly defined variables and meta-data.
- To compare and contrast different options for data storage in open access repositories.

To write a data management plan for a cultivar evaluation trial that covers good data management throughout the lifecycle of the project and future sharing and reusing of research data.

Unit 9.1 – Introduction to data management pt 1

Lecturer(s): Julia Cooper, PhD

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Organic Research Centre (ORC)

Unit duration: 1h00

Topics: This unit introduces the key terminology relating to research data with a focus on types of data with examples and data management plans. Learners review training materials that put “Research data in context” and participate in a group discussion on the topic. Data management plans are introduced and their importance explained; learners are introduced to the structure of a typical data management plan.

Unit 9.2 - Introduction to data management pt 2

Lecturer(s): Julia Cooper, PhD

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Organic Research Centre (ORC)

Unit duration: 1h20

Topics: In this unit learners are provided with more detail on key topics essential in data management including: naming variables, research data documentation, metadata and GDPR. They are provided with an example to learn more about metadata and documentation. They complete an activity using the ICASA dictionary. At the end of this unit there is a mid-module online quiz to test their understanding of the theory behind data management.

Unit 9.3 - Practical examples

Lecturer(s): Julia Cooper, PhD

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Organic Research Centre (ORC)

Unit duration: 1h00

Topics: In this Unit learners will be guided through a set of self-directed activities to broaden their understanding of key topics in data management. This will include an exercise using the “Fieldbook app” online and/or on their phones as an example of a digital tool for data collection. They will also be introduced to the various open-access repositories for agricultural data. Activities will help them to critically assess the quality of data in these repositories and how well it meets the principles of FAIR data.

Unit 9.4 - Data management plan

Lecturer(s): Julia Cooper, PhD

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Organic Research Centre (ORC)

Unit duration: 3h00

Topics: Learners are given the opportunity to develop a data management plan for their on-farm cultivar evaluation trial project, or choosing a hypothetical scenario from Module 8. They will be provided with a 7 part data management plan to use as a template. They can submit their plan to the module instructor for feedback.

Module 10 - Application of digital tools for data collection and sharing

Materials available on: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56307/>

Links to the quizzes or other exercises:

Module 10 Unit 10.1: <https://forms.gle/XbgH3LbG3ojk1AFg6>

Module 10 Unit 10.2:

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSd3w9HWJmqPypCDGsqgGgcFCUSnwznhv3eywsInGUaTnQTdMQ/viewform>

Module 10 Unit 10.3:

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeIXqoPMCCiyEe2BiUsQdQBE0vFk02po4OUNzqYbC4-ih0TeA/viewform>

Module 10 Unit 10.4: <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfYvFnL8S0luyvIv-XQXaS-MS32ttZFJVykl6rTc1AjO3XUuw/viewform>

Number of units: 5

Topics: Module 10 focuses on the use of digital tools for data collection and sharing.

- Unit 1 explains the importance of these tools in organic farming, research, and organisational work, highlighting widely used platforms such as SeedLinked, ClimMob, and iNaturalist.
- Unit 2 provides a detailed description of how SeedLinked works, including its data protection features.
- Unit 3 offers practical guidance for experiment leaders and producers on using SeedLinked.
- Unit 4 presents case studies demonstrating the benefits of digital tools in practice.
- Unit 5 contains practical exercises and test settings for participants to prepare experiments, involve growers, and plan data collection.

The module as a whole provides both theoretical knowledge and practical skills for the effective use of digital tools in organic breeding and variety evaluation.

Target groups: trial managers and growers.

Learning objectives: At the end of the training, the trainee will be able to:

- Understand the role of digital tools in organic farming and research.
- Select and compare different digital data collection platforms.
- Use the SeedLinked system to plan and conduct experiments.
- Draw inspiration from case studies for their own projects.
- Perform practical test settings on the SeedLinked interface.
- Organize experiments in a structured manner with the involvement of growers.

- Prepare analyses from the data obtained from the experiments.
- Use the checklists and questionnaires presented in the module to prepare for the work.
- Effectively link digital tools to practical breeding and cultivation processes.

Unit 10.1 – Why is it important to apply digital tools for data collection and sharing?

Lecturer(s): Gyöngyi Györéné Kis, PhD

LIVESEEDING partner(s): ÖMKi

Unit duration: 35 min

Topics: This module video examines the role of digital tools in data collection and sharing, with a focus on their applications in agriculture, research, and organisational management. It highlights the key features and benefits of widely used platforms in organic farming and research, including SeedLinked, ClimMob, iNaturalist, Field Book, BrAPI, Datar, Phenome Networks, QuickTrials, and AgriPartner.

The video provides a clear, side-by-side comparison of these tools for supporting on-farm trials, biodiversity monitoring, data collection, and breeding programme management. It also explains why the module focuses specifically on SeedLinked over other tools. Finally, participants can assess their understanding of the unit by completing an interactive quiz.

Unit 10.2 - SeedLinked Platform Overview

Lecturer(s): Nicolas Enjalbert, PhD

LIVESEEDING subcontractor: SeedLinked

Unit duration: 8 min

Topics: This module video introduces the SeedLinked platform as the digital backbone for collaborative trialing, data collection, and sharing. It highlights its trait ontology (standard 1–5 scoring, yield data, photos, comments, binary questions, trial conditions), flexible trial design options (non-replicated, triadic randomization, full set, subset, survey, single-site, and tasting evaluations), and strict data privacy (GDPR compliance, grower data ownership). The platform has been localized into ten languages and is active in 16 EU countries, ensuring accessibility and regional adaptation.

Unit 10.3 - Tutorial for trial managers (and growers) on how to use SeedLinked

Lecturer(s): Nicolas Enjalbert, PhD

LIVESEEDING subcontractor: SeedLinked

Unit duration: 8 min

Topics: This module video develops training resources so both trial managers and growers can confidently use SeedLinked. It includes video tutorials on setting up and running trials (from variety creation to tasting evaluations), using the mobile app, and analyzing results. Separate “getting started” guides for growers ensure usability at all levels. Quizzes are included to reinforce learning and verify understanding. These materials aim to standardize trial processes and lower the barrier to digital adoption.

Unit 10.4 - Case Examples from Ongoing Trials

Unit duration: 30 min

Lecturer(s): Nicolas Enjalbert, PhD, Matteo Petitti

LIVESEEDING partner(s)/subcontractor(s): SeedLinked, RSR, ÖMKi

Topics: This module provides concrete examples of collaborative breeding and trialing to illustrate how SeedLinked is applied in practice. For instance, a video case study from the USA on pepper and tomato breeding demonstrates participatory methods and digital data capture. These serve as learning tools and inspiration for project partners, connecting theory with real-world implementation.

Unit 10.5 - Practical Exercises and Trial Setup

Lecturer(s): Nicolas Enjalbert, PhD

LIVESEEDING partner(s)/subcontractor(s): SeedLinked, ÖMKi

Unit duration: 4 min

Topics: This module guides partners through hands-on trial setup, from defining crops, regions, growers, and varieties to planning seed distribution, planting, and data collection. A “First Trial Questionnaire” helps organizers clarify objectives, traits of interest, and logistical details. Grower recruitment strategies are also addressed. Partners are encouraged to test the system by creating demo accounts, practicing data entry, and simulating trials via the mobile app. Practical checklists and quizzes ensure readiness before real trial launches.

Materials

The available materials for each Module include:

- The **Training Outline** summarizing concepts and learning objectives for each training module;
- The corresponding **PowerPoint (PPT)** presentations for each unit;
- The **video recordings** of each unit;
- **Infographics** regarding some topics;
- **Quizzes** to test trainee's knowledge and give feedback on their understanding;
- The **additional materials** suggested in the presentations are intended to widen the learning process (i) scientific and public papers, ii) online available tutorials, iii) links to digital tools for data collection and sharing iv) links to projects, etc.);
- Training materials will be updated for selected modules, after their in-person delivery at the LIVESEEDING final year Summer School.

Additional lectures and video recordings are expected to be integrated into certain units (e.g., Module 6 Unit 6.1 and Module 10 Unit 10.4) over the coming months, particularly in preparation for the Summer School, while maintaining the same Organic Eprint link.

Table 1. List of training materials available in Organic EPrints and ECO-PB repositories.

	Links to Organic EPrints
Module 6	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56300/
Module 7	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56302/
Module 8	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56304/
Module 9	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56306/
Module 10	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56307/

Learning assessment for the Units

Assessment will be carried out in several forms, related to the modules. Assessment methods include:

- Online quizzes (self-assessment and module-closing tests, e.g. on Google Forms)
- Practical tasks, simulations (e.g. data entry in R, setting up SeedLinked trials)

In the summer school organised by LiveSeeding in July 2026: Case study presentation (processing and presentation of specific practical examples) and Verbal feedback and discussion (during training sessions and webinars)

Links to the quizzes or other exercises:

Module 6 Unit 6.1: <https://forms.gle/YVdbHSZ7E6XgTySF8>

Module 6 Unit 6.2: <https://forms.gle/cxdovirv3eqtpZT7A>

Module 7 Unit 7.1: <https://forms.gle/FhCSQUYvxvixEmAq6>

Module 7 Unit 7.2: <https://forms.gle/M4WG1i7MvmGqDQ468>

Module 7 Unit 7.3: <https://forms.gle/JPAYjDgsWH1BhNM2A>

Module 7 Unit 7.4: <https://forms.gle/8vevQxfVofevwnEY8>

Module 7 Unit 7.5: <https://forms.gle/W8byTQg2ndgm1isx6>

Module 8 Unit 8.1 & 8.2:

Quiz: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeJOfn3KYXVx1FbdTw1RVnUIP6CC0viFS_w3NM0mBPYdUWOUA/viewform

Unit 8.3: Citizen science exercise and Unit 8.4: Scenario exercise: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56304/>

Module 9 Unit 9.1 & 9.2:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdSssDfhr6tbr5eXqzc_-w-CdrkHtoNmeu2ELbROEKHZnYMw/formResponse

Module 9 Unit 9.3 & 9.4: Trainees participate in a variety of self-directed learning activities in Unit 9.3 and create their own Data Management Plan in Unit 9.4. These activities can be assessed by peers or the instructor. <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56306/>

Module 10 Unit 10.1: <https://forms.gle/XbgH3LbG3ojk1AFg6>

Module 10 Unit 10.2:

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSd3w9HWJmqPypCDGsqgGgcFCUSnwznhv3eywsInGUaTnQTdMQ/viewform>

Module 10 Unit 10.3:

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeIXqoPMCCiyEe2BiUsQdQBE0vFk02po4OUNzqYbC4-ih0TeA/viewform>

Module 10 Unit 10.4: <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfYvFnL8S0luyvIv-XQXaS-MS32ttZFJVykl6rTc1AjO3XUuw/viewform>

References:

Rey, F., Rivière, P., Flipon, E., de Buck, A., Fehér, J., Costanzo, A., & Lazzaro, M. (2021). *Frugal, multi-actor and decentralised cultivar evaluation models for organic agriculture: Methods, tools and guidelines (Deliverable D2.3)*. LIVESEED project.